

DEVELOPMENT OF CONCRETE COMPOSITION WITH THE HELP OF CHEMICAL ADDITIVES OF HIGH STRENGTH HEAVY CONCRETE

Botirova Nodira Sherali qizi¹

student

Abdikomilova Mohinur Jamoliddin qizi²

student

Botirov Bektosh Farhod o'g'li³

assistant

Abdullayev Mardon Axmat o'g'li⁴

assistant

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology Guliston branch

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7298195>

Аннотация: В данной статье изучено описание цементного вяжущего и наполнителя для определения физико-механических свойств тяжелого бетона с повышенной прочностью.

Ключевые слова: Время твердения цементного теста, цемент, наполнитель.

Today, monolithic construction requires high strength concretes and their use. It is known that such concretes have a dense structure and differ in terms of application and technological properties. Their strength varies widely, i.e. from 21 to 67 MPa (classes B35...B45). By choosing the right composition and raw materials, it is possible to get cold-resistant, waterproof, fast-hardening, high-strength, fire-resistant and other concretes.

The ratio between the materials used in the design of the concrete structure should be selected in such a way that, taking into account the preparation technology, the strength of the concrete in the structure, the mobility of the concrete mixture and the cost-effectiveness of the concrete (minimal reduction of cement consumption) should be guaranteed.

The design of concrete composition included the following: determination of requirements for concrete based on the type of structure, conditions of use and preparation method, selection of materials for concrete and obtaining the necessary information describing their properties, determination of the primary composition of concrete, hardened concrete for the sample checking of the composition of the mixture, control of the concrete preparation process, preparation time, properties of fillers and other factors, corrections were made to its composition.

Determination of the initial composition of concrete was carried out based on the dependence of concrete strength on cement activity, water-cement ratio, quality of materials used, mobility of concrete mixture, water consumption and other factors.

In order to clearly determine the properties of concrete and the extent to which the concrete mixture depends on its composition, preliminary tests were carried out. In this case, the analytical method of planning the experiment and studying its results was used. The requirements for concrete strength are shown in the working drawings.

The placement of the concrete mixture is easy only when the amount of cement in the composition is sufficient. If the amount of cement is less than the specified level, the risk of the separation of the concrete mixture into layers, the appearance of micro-voids in it and the reduction of the service life increases.

Based on the results of the analysis, the optimal composition of the concrete mixture was selected, and samples were prepared according to this composition. As a result of laboratory analysis, the limits of compressive strength for 3, 7 and 28 days were checked. Tables 1-2 show the working compositions with the highest values of each concrete class (B35, B40, B45) according to the verified results.

Working composition of concrete mixture without chemical additives

Table

1

Mahsulot nomi	Harakatlanuv chanlik	Beton klassi (marka)	1 m ³ beton qorishmasining ishchi tarkibi					
			PS 500 D0	Qum (yirik)	qum (mayda)	Chaqiq tosh (5-20 mm)	Polimix X1 405 S	Suv
			kg	kg	kg	kg	kg	l
Og'ir beton qorishmasi	P4(16-20)	B35 (M400)	415	671	287	770	-	215
		B40 (M500)	440	636	272	797	-	216
		B45 (M600)	460	610	261	811	-	220

Properties of concrete samples with chemical additives

Table

№	Namuna olingan sana	Namuna olingan vaqt	Namuna zinalgan sana	Sutka	Betoning o'rtacha zichligi, kg/m ³	O'lov apparatining ko'rsatkichi, Mpa	O'lov ko'rsatkichi 0,95		Beton klassi (marka)	Mustahkamlik, %	Harorat (°C)	Namlik (%)
							Alohida ko'rsatkich	O'rtacha ko'rsatkich				
1	31.03.2022	11:50	03.04.2022	3	2390	21,6	21	21,5	B35 (M400)	46,8	22°C	69%
					2398	24,8	22					
			07.04.2022	7	2386	38,4	36,4	36,7		79,9		
					2380	39	37					
			28.04.2022	28	2400	52,1	49	50		109		
2391	52,5	51										
2	03.04.2022	11:50	06.04.2022	3	2405	41,2	39,3	39,4	B40 (M550)	75,4	21°C	72%
					2405	41,6	39,5					
			10.04.2022	7	2401	49	46	48,7		93,1		
					2408	51,2	49,4					
			01.05.2022	28	2399	60,1	58,1	58,2		111,3		
2405	61	58,3										
3	05.04.2022	9:38	08.04.2022	3	2401	41,5	39,5	39,6	B45 (M600)	67,4	22°C	69%
					2413	43	39,7					
			12.04.2022	7	2412	53,1	51	51,5		87,6		
					2420	54	52					
			03.05.2022	28	2422	63	61,4	61,7		104,8		
2409	64,1	67										

The optimal working composition of the concrete mixture with chemical additives

Table 2

Mahsulot nomi	Harakatlanuvchanlik	Beton klassi (marka)	1 m ³ beton qarishmasining ishchi tarkibi					
			PS 500 D0	Qum (yirik)	qum (mayda)	Chaqiq tosh (5-20 mm)	Polimix X1 345 S	Suv
			kg	kg	kg	kg	kg	l
Og'ir beton qarishmasi	P4(16-20)	B35 (M400)	375	759	325	740	4,3	170
		B40 (M500)	400	734	315	754	4,8	169
		B45 (M600)	420	709	304	772	5,3	168

Picture 1. Compressive strength of concrete without and with chemical additives

In conclusion, the technical and economic efficiency of obtaining high-strength concrete with the complex use of local natural and mineral raw materials and chemical additives consisted of the following factors:

1. Use of cheap and infrequently required local raw materials, including mineral waste;
2. Saving cement (1.5-2.0 times) by replacing it with natural mineral fillers;
3. A significant decrease in the cost of economic costs for the supply and use of high-quality imported raw materials for concrete;
4. Due to the almost absolute water resistance of these concrete compositions, it is possible to use high-strength concrete without additional thermal insulation based on mineral binders in structures operating in wet environments.

References:

1. Баженов Ю.М. Высокопрочный бетон на основе пластификаторов / Ю.М. Баженов и др. // Бетон и железобетон. 1978. - №9. - С. 18-19.
2. Баженов Ю.М. Модифицированные высококачественные бетоны: научное издание / Ю.М. Баженов, В.С. Демьянова, В.И. Калашников. М.: Издательство Ассоциации строительных вузов, 2006. - 368 с.
3. Akramov X.A., Nuriddinov X.I., Rakhimov Sh.T., Turopov M.T., "Technology of concrete aggregates". Study guide. T., Taki, 2010-167b.
4. Akramov X. A., Gaziev U. A. Production of concrete and reinforced concrete based on industrial waste. - T.: Taki. 2012. 253 p.

5. Хакимов, О., & Қурбонов, З. (2022). ПЛАСТИКЛИГИ КАМ ТУПРОҚЛАР АСОСИДА ЕНГИЛ ТЎЛДИРУВЧИЛАР ОЛИШ ИМКОНИАТЛАРИНИ ЎРГАНИШ. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 1(5), 58-64.
6. Kurbanov, Z., & Parsaeva, N. (2022, June). Strong grinding based on local raw materials getting stones. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2432, No. 1, p. 030104). AIP Publishing LLC.
7. Ganiev, A., Tursunov, B. A., & Kurbanov, Z. K. (2022). Prospects for the use of multiple vermiculitis. *Science and Education*, 3(4), 409-414.
8. Ганиев, А., угли Турсунов, Б. А., & Курбанов, З. Х. (2022). Особо легких бетонов полученных на основе сельского хозяйственных отходов. *Science and Education*, 3(4), 492-498.
9. Ганиев, А., Қурбонов, З. Х., Усанова, Г. А., & Назаров, Ж. Ж. Ў. (2022). Тоғ-кон саноати чиқиндилари асосида олинадиган майда донали бетонлар. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 258-263.
10. Курбанов, З. Х., Ганиев, А., & Усанова, Г. А. (2022). ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ СОСТАВА СУХОЙ СТРОИТЕЛЬНОЙ СМЕСИ НА ОСНОВЕ МРАМОРНЫХ ОТХОДОВ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(1), 299-304.
11. Khamidulloevich, K. Z., Begalievich, A. K., & Sanjarbek, K. (2021). TECHNOLOGY OF PRODUCTION OF EARTH WORKS WITH THE APPLICATION OF GEOGRAPHS. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(5), 267-271.
12. Курбанов, З. Х. угли Холбоев, СО (2021). Микроарматурализация сухих строительных смесей волластонитом. *Science and Education*, 2(5), 410-416.
13. Farhod o'g'li, B. B. (2022, September). YUQORI MUSTANKAMLIKKA EGA BO 'LGAN OG 'IR BETON UCHUN SEMENT VA TO 'LDIRUVCHINING TAVSIFI. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION"* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 11-117).
14. Farhod o'g'li, B. B., & Berdiyev, O. B. (2022). Optimal Composition and Study of The Physical and Mechanical Properties of High-Strength Heavy Concrete. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability* (2660-9630), 16, 14-17.
15. Расулова, Н., & Бобокулова, Ш. (2022). ЗАМОНАВИЙ ПЕЧЛАР ЁРДАМИДА СОПОЛ БУЮМЛАР ИШЛАБ ЧИҚАРИШ УСУЛЛАРИ. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 1(4), 122-127.

16. Rasulova, N., & Boboqulova, S. (2022). BETONNING SUV O 'TKAZUVCHANLIGINI VA UNING MUSTAXKAMLIGINI YAXSHILASH USULLARI. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 1(4), 128-133.
17. Aziza, K. (2022). Ecological Concrete on Base Concrete-Building Waste. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability* (2660-9630), 14, 87-90.
18. Begalievich, A. K., & Abdulazizovich, B. A. (2022). Efficiency of Obtaining Wall Materials from Industrial Waste. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 1(7), 134-139.
19. Абдусаматов, К. Б. (2022). Исследовательская работа по определению теплопроводности и термическое сопротивление образцов газобетона. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 244-248.
20. Баходиров, А. А., & Абдусаматов, К. Б. (2020). перспективы использования асбестоцементных отходов в качестве микрофибры при производстве газобетона. *IEJRD-Международный междисциплинарный журнал*, 5(7), 5.
21. Nurmamatov, N. R., & Tilavov, E. N. O. G. L. (2022). Bazalt tolasi asosida fibrabeton optimal tarkibini tanlash va fizik mexanik xossalarini taxlili. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 153-160.
22. Нурмаматов, Н. Р. (2022). Изучение процесса получения пенобетона на основе местного синтетического сырья. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 291-295.
23. Nurmamatov, N. R. (2022). Bazalt armatura ishlab chiqarishdagi chiqindi asosida fibrabeton tarkibini tanlash va xossalarini o'rganish. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 146-152.
24. Istamov, Y., & O'roqboyev, O. B. (2022). YUQORI MUSTAHKAM BETONLAR OLISHDA KIMYOVIY VA MINERAL QO'SHIMCHALAR YORDAMIDA FIZIK-MEXANIK XOSSALARINI TADQIQ ETISH. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(1), 310-318.
25. Nurmamatov, N. R., & Tilavov, E. N. O. G. L. (2022). Bazalt tolasi asosida fibrabeton optimal tarkibini tanlash va fizik mexanik xossalarini taxlili. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 153-160.
26. Nurmamatov, N. R. (2022). Bazalt armatura ishlab chiqarishdagi chiqindi asosida fibrabeton tarkibini tanlash va xossalarini o'rganish. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 146-152.
27. Nazirboyevich, A. R. (2022, September). SELECTION OF THE OPTIMAL COMPOSITION OF FIBER CONCRETE BASED ON BASALT FIBERS AND ANALYSIS OF PHYSICAL MECHANICAL PROPERTIES. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC*

CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION" (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 57-65).

28. Rasul, A. (2022). KO'PCHITILGAN VERMIKULITNING YENGIL BETONLARDA QO'LLANILISHI VA BETON KIRISHISHI. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(10), 50-53.

29. Yusuf, I., & Tursunov, B. A. (2022). SANOAT CHIQINDISI VA MINERAL QO'SHIMCHALAR ASOSIDA OLINGAN SEMENTLARNING FIZIK-MEXANIK XOSSALARINI O'RGANISH. Journal of Integrated Education and Research, 1(1), 324-329.

30. Tursunov, B. A. (2019). The usage of composite armature in construction.

31. Tursunov, B. A. (2019). ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF COMPOSITE AND STEEL ARMATURE. In Строительные материалы, конструкции и технологии XXI века (pp. 87-88).

32. Khakimov, O. M. (2022). Issiq-quruq iqlim sharoiti uchun asfaltbeton tarkibini tanlash. Science and Education, 3(2), 241-247.

33. Азимов, Б. С. (2022, September). ИЗВЕСТКОВЫЙ СТРОИТЕЛЬНЫЙ РАСТВОР ДЛЯ ОТДЕЛКИ СТЕН ЗДАНИЙ ИЗ ГАЗОБЕТОНА. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION" (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 73-79).

34. Ochiltoshevich, E. S. (2016). Organizational and structural measures to improve the process of operation concrete span. European science review, (9-10), 184-186.

35. Шодмонов, А. Ю. (2021). Изучение свойств базальтового фибробетона. Современное промышленное и гражданское строительство, 17(2), 77-84.

36. Шодмонов, А. Ю. (2021). Исследование механических свойств базальтового бетона. Science and Education, 2(5), 250-256.

37. Botirqulovna, R. N. (2022). KIMYOVIY QO 'SHIMCHANING YENGIL BETONLARNING FEZIK-MEXANIK XOSSALARIGA TA'SIRINI O 'RGANISH. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(10), 54-56.

38. Mirzayeva, I., & Mo'minov, A. (2022). O 'TA YENGIL KO 'PIK POLISTIROLBETON ISHLAB CHIQRISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Инновационные исследования в науке, 1(15), 57-63.

39. Ганиев, А. Г. (2019). Исследование влияния суперпластификатора на свойства бетона. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире, (12-1), 41-43.

40. Ганиев, А. Г. (2018). О гидратных новообразованиях в цементном бетоне при его циклическом замораживании. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире, (1-1), 6-11.

